

Integrating Language Skills: Working with Lp-Sp-Rvg-Wvg Model

Binoy Barman*

***Abstract:** Listening, speaking, reading and writing are four basic skills of learning a language, first or second, native or foreign. Related to them are three sub-skills, namely, pronunciation, vocabulary and grammar. One way of teaching/learning of these skills, in the second/foreign language environments, is integrating them into a single package, rather than keeping them separate or segregated. This paper offers a model of integrating these skills, so that teachers may teach a language effectively and the learners can learn and use it easily. The model has been explained with example for the better understanding of teachers and learners. The people in language teaching profession may bring it to classroom and test its efficacy, and ultimately remodel it to their own needs.*

***Keywords:** Integration, segregation, listening, speaking, reading, writing*

1. Introduction

The complete learning of a language means acquisition of four major skills – listening, speaking, reading and writing and three sub-skills – pronunciation, vocabulary and grammar. The skills can be taught either in a segregated or in an integrated way. The former entails an analytic approach whereby the skills are taught/learnt piecemeal in separate classes. The latter, on the other hand, takes a synthetic approach whereby all the skills go together in classes. The principal benefit of integration of skills is that every class meets all necessary aspects of a language and the learners get a total view of it. Through sufficient practice, they develop the language efficiency in a concerted fashion and gradually become able to use it with confidence. Well versed in all skills, they become perfect users of the language they have learned. Segregation is not desirable unless an individual or a group of learners are not in special need of a modular enhancement through a tailored course of grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation or any of the four skills, for overcoming perceptible lacking in the particular area. For general learning of a language, integration of skills is always preferable.

*Daffodil Institute of Languages (DIL), and Associate Profcssor, Department of English, Daffodil International University, Dhaka, Bangladcsh

This paper presents a model of integrating language skills dubbed “Lp-Sp-Rvg-Wvg Model”. This model shows that the four skills can be ordered as listening-speaking-reading-writing, listening and speaking being attached to pronunciation, and reading and writing to vocabulary and grammar. Not ruling out the possibility of other combinations, the model claims that the skills are best integrated when put in the mentioned order and would produce the best results in an SLT/FLT program. The model engages students in constant sequential practice, directed by teacher, who prepares/selects a syllabus and accordingly use materials suitable for a group of learners. One prerequisite for its success is that the teacher has to be well-trained in pedagogy and efficient in language skills management.

2. Methodological Issues

With careful reflection and planning, any teacher can integrate the skills to facilitate language teaching and learning. When the skills are woven together in an effective way, learners can improve their language efficiency rapidly. Traditionally, reading and writing skills are given preference in a language classroom. Listening and speaking skills can easily be combined with the other two in a CLT framework.

The methodology in which all the language skills are integrated is sometimes called ‘Integrated Skills Approach’. The methodological tapestry leads to optimal L2 communication when the skills are interwoven during instruction (Barman and Basu 2015). Richards, Platt and Weber (1985) define Integrated Skills Approach as: “the teaching of the language skills of reading writing, listening and speaking in conjunction with each other as when a lesson involves activities that relate listening and speaking to reading and writing” (p. 144). They think, with tasks that expose students to these skills in conjunction, they will gain a deeper understanding of how communication works in the foreign language and become more motivated when they see the value of performing meaningful activities in the classroom.

Lubelska and Matthews (1997) put forth seven observations, akin to guidelines, regarding integration of language skills:

- i) Integrated skills involve using some or all of listening, speaking, reading and writing to practice new material (vocabulary, pronunciation, grammar, text/discourse).
- ii) All four skills must be practiced in every lesson.

- iii) All listening and speaking naturally go together, so it is desirable to integrate these two skills.
- iv) The sequence hear-speak-read-write is the most appropriate for integrated skills work.
- v) A common topic, such as holiday or pets, is a device linking the separate activities in integrated skills lessons.
- vi) If we want to develop specific sub-skills (reading for gist, guessing unknown words, etc.) it is necessary to focus on individual skills in some lessons.
- vii) Integrated skills may be fine with a small group of adults, but it is difficult to do with large classes and in lessons lasting only 35 minutes.

In the making of our model, we have taken the fourth observation of Lubelska and Matthews (1997) as a basic tenet, which has determined the sequence of four major skills of language.

Barman and Basu (2015) identify two forms of instruction that are oriented towards integration of skills: a) Content-based instruction, and b) Task-based instruction. In Content-based instruction, students practice all the language skills in a highly integrated communicative fashion while learning content such as science, business, law or sociology. In Task-based instruction, students participate in communicative tasks in authentic language where attention is principally paid to meaning rather than form. Oxford (2001) advocates integrated skills approach, over segregated skills approach, for the tremendous advantages that it offers for the learners. We can summarize the advantages of integration as follows:

- i) It exposes the second language learners to authentic language instances.
- ii) It involves the learners in activities that are interesting and meaningful.
- iii) It compels the learners to interact naturally in the language which becomes not just an object of academic interest but a real means of interaction among people.
- iv) Learners rapidly gain a true picture of the richness and complexity of L2 as employed for communication.
- v) Teachers are in a position to track students' progress in multiple skills at the same time.

- vi) It promotes learning of the real content, not just the dissection of language forms.
- vii) It allows a balanced and mutually supportive growth in all the main skills and the subsidiary skills.
- viii) When productive and receptive skills are integrated, they become complementary for each other, conducive to enhanced acquisition.
- ix) One single topic can be fully explored and the same text or context can be used for multiple activities.
- x) It can be highly motivating to students of all ages and backgrounds.

3. Basics of Four Skills

3.1 Listening

Listening is a receptive skill playing a crucial role in the comprehension of language. It is also a prerequisite for verbal communication as it provides primary input for language build-up. Verbal communication is a bilateral process where listening is intertwined with speaking. Speaking does not of itself constitute communication unless what is said is comprehended by another person (Rivers, 1968). White (2008) says, "Being a good listener involves collaborating with speakers and taking an active role in asking for clarification when you do not understand....Effective listening also involves empathizing with the speaker and trying to use things from his/her point of view" (p. 13). To say something in response to somebody, one needs to understand what has already been said. Listening skill involves recognition of sounds and identification of words along with their meanings. Therefore it is a part and parcel of our thinking process. It is deeply integrated with our perception of life and the world.

We should be aware of two different uses of the term *listening*. In general sense, listening is attending to any aural signal that hits the eardrum. And in restrictive sense, listening is being able to understand the linguistic signals that enter the brain through ears. We refer to the second sense of listening when we talk of language skill vis-à-vis ESL/EFL/ELT. The first sense, which is sometimes branded as *hearing*, is important for the communication theorists. The two senses of listening are, however, cannot be separated. Linguistic listening is an integral part of communicative listening. The former forms the basis for the latter.

Listening involves a sender (speaker), a message, and a receiver (the listener). Listeners process in their brain what they have just heard, trying to figure out the meaning. They have to cope with the sender's choice of vocabulary, structure, and rate of delivery. The difficulty of the listening process is multiplied in second language contexts, where the receiver has incomplete control of the language. Listening is not a passive act, as it is often thought. Rather it is an active process which involves paying attention to the speaker's words as well as someone's own thoughts and ideas (Gebhard, 2009, p. 149).

Listening is connected to the interactional and transactional functions of language. Interactional exchanges establish social relationship between speakers and listeners. Transactional exchanges help listeners to comprehend the content of the speaker's message. Listening in fact completes the discourse. That is why Rost (1990) sees the listener in certain circumstances as 'co-authoring' the discourse, not just waiting to be talked to and to respond, but by his responses actually helping to construct it.

Rost (2011, p. 2-3) observes, listening has four orientations or perspectives: receptive, constructive, collaborative and transformative. That is, listening may mean: a) receiving what the speaker actually says; b) constructing and representing meaning; c) negotiating meaning with the speaker and responding; and d) creating meaning through involvement, imagination and empathy. In SLT/FLT environment, the learner often adopts such macro-strategies as predicting, monitoring, responding, clarifying, inferencing and evaluating (Lynch, 2007, p. 16).

3.2 Speaking

Speaking is often considered to be the most important skill of a language, be it first or second. In fact, day-to-day human communication is mostly performed by speaking. Without it, human communication is crippled. Speaking is the direct route from one mind to another, and is the way we usually choose when we want to ask a question or give an answer (Turk, 2003). In many contexts, speaking is often the skill upon which a person is judged at face value (McDonough and Shaw, 2004). All people, whether literate or illiterate, barring the retarded and disabled ones, have the capacity to speak. Every person, as a first language speaker, gets this skill naturally, through social interaction while growing up. But it is different for a second/foreign language learner. He/she has to struggle much to acquire this skill.

Speaking is a productive skill, which calls for people's performance. Speakers perform in a situation of communication. It is the test of learning of a language or the measure of knowing a language. It is more complicated than it apparently appears and involves much more than just uttering words. Through speaking, a person verbalises thoughts and ideas processed in the brain. Speaking is contrasted with writing which is also a productive skill. Hughes (2011) notes, while written discourse is static, visual/motoric, non-transient, planned and de-contextualized, spoken discourse is dynamic, oral/aural, transient, unplanned and context-dependent.

Speaking skill may refer to several phenomena. First, it may refer to the ability to utter any sound; second, it may refer to communication in any language; and third, it may refer to the ability to impress others with nice talks. In ESL/EFL/ELT, we are concerned with the second meaning. This skill is to be acquired with constant practice with the help of teachers or other means. Canale and Swain (1980) argue that the ability to communicate requires four different sub-competencies:

- i) *grammatical* (ability to create grammatically correct utterances),
- ii) *sociolinguistic* (ability to produce sociolinguistically appropriate utterances),
- iii) *discourse* (ability to produce coherent and cohesive utterances), and
- iv) *strategic* (ability to solve communication problems as they arise).

Speaking is largely dependent on listening. Without listening, nobody can become a speaker, which is proven by the fact that those who are deaf never learn to speak. Speaking is an important aspect of interaction, the manifestation of verbal communication. Speaking and listening together form an interactive event. According to Bygate (2008, p. 7), interactive skills involve the ability to use language in order to satisfy two specific conditions: a) processing condition (there is brain to process information), and b) reciprocity condition (two or more people are engaged in exchanging information). In the communicative model of language teaching, instructors help their students develop this body of knowledge by providing authentic practice that prepares students for real-life interactions.

3.3 Reading

Reading skill comes in parallel with writing skill. It is the receptive skill as it involves taking in printed information. Reading boosts up vocabulary development that in turn helps listening comprehension. For the child

learners, reading just means recognising orthographical symbols or alphabets and their arrangement into words. At the advanced level, it will mean decoding texts. Therefore, there are two levels of meaning: identification and interpretation. The former might be identified as a lower level skill and the latter as a higher level skill. Silberstein (1994) says:

Fluent readers seem to simultaneously employ what have come to be known as lower level skills that allow them to rapidly and automatically recognize words (and presumably grammatical forms), while higher level skills allow them to comprehend and interpret. Lower level skills involve rapid and precise unconscious processing (automaticity). (p. 6-7)

As for reading, there is a certain measure of subjectivity in the interpretation of texts. Texts may be understood in different ways by different readers. There are also different objectives of reading for different readers. Williams (1984) broadly identifies three main purposes: a) getting general information from the text, b) getting specific information from the text, and c) for pleasure or interest. Grabe and Stoller (2011, p. 13) list the reading purposes as follows:

- i) Reading to search for simple information
- ii) Reading to skim quickly
- iii) Reading to learn from texts
- iv) Reading to integrate information
- v) Reading to write (or search for information needed for writing)
- vi) Reading to critique texts
- vii) Reading for general comprehension

Reading may develop independently of listening and speaking or in conjunction with them. In many societies literature is seen as the prime example of writing and therefore students are encouraged to read (McDonough and Shaw, 2004). Wallace (2010) observes, reading is so much part of daily life for those who live in literate communities that we hardly consider either the purposes or processes involved. Technological societies operate on the premise that their members can read. He adds, "In the real world, effective reading means a flexible and appropriate response to the material in hand, and this is always guided by the reader's purpose; it means that readers are aware that they have options, including the option to give up" (Wallace, 2010, p. 5).

From theoretical perspectives, reading is a dynamic process in which the text elements interact with other factors outside the text. The process of reconstructing meaning is one of mapping the linguistic content onto extralinguistic context. Learning to read in L1 and L2 setting is different. Reading proficiency in the second or foreign language does not develop as completely or easily as it usually does in one's first language. Grabe and Stoller (2011, p. 2) regret, "Seldom are L2 students given as much time to develop strong reading abilities, despite similarly demanding expectations for success."

3.4 Writing

Writing is a productive skill, in parallel with speaking, contrasted with reading on receptive side. It is a visual form of communication, which is usually recorded in paper, through printing or handwriting. It is thought to be the most difficult of the four language skills, sometimes difficult even for the native speakers, as it is not just a graphic representation of speech, but the presentation of thoughts in a structured way. In writing, one needs to be very careful with every word and every sentence, in logical presentation of information, maintaining writing conventions including punctuation and spelling. Writing is a sophisticated act, which calls for some crafting skills. Hedge (2005, p. 10) talks of the following crafting skills:

- i) Getting the grammar right
- ii) Having a range of vocabulary
- iii) Punctuating meaningfully
- iv) Using the conventions of layout correctly
- v) Spelling accurately
- vi) Using the range of sentence structures
- vii) Linking ideas and information across sentences to develop a topic
- viii) Developing and organizing the content clearly and convincingly

Writing is an aspect of communication that allows a person to compose thoughts and ideas, and note it down for other people to read. Psycholinguist Eric Lenneberg (1967) noted that human beings universally learn to walk and to talk, but writing is not universal in that sense. We learn to write if we are members of a literate society, and if only someone teaches us. Like reading, writing is generally a silent, reflective activity. In pedagogy, writing is seen from three different perspectives which are often termed as approaches. Hyland (2011, p. 7-8) clarifies the three approaches:

- i) The first approach focuses on the products of writing by examining texts, either through their formal surface elements or their discourse structure.
- ii) The second approach, divided into expressivist, cognitivist and situational strands, focuses on the writer and describes writing in terms of the process used to create texts.
- iii) The third approach emphasizes the role that readers play in writing, adding a social dimension to writing by elaborating how writers engage with an audience in creating texts.

According to Raimes (1983), writing has a wide range of concerns including syntax, grammar, mechanics, organization, word choice, purpose, audience and content. Writing skill has several levels. The first level involves handwriting, spelling and punctuation. The second level involves grammar and vocabulary. The third level involves paragraph. And the fourth level involves overall organisation. Writing skill develop through the four levels, starting from the most basic one (level one) up to the highest one (level four). The levels are shown with the following diagram (McDonough and Shaw, 2004):

Figure-1: Levels of skills

The input for writing often comes from reading. Ample reading is necessary as a preparation for good writing. An efficient writer is necessarily an efficient reader. Welty (2002) observes, "Indeed, learning to write may be part of learning to read. For all I know, writing comes out of a superior devotion to reading." For learning a language, Raimes (1983) lays great

emphasis on writing practice. She points out three specific advantages of writing (p. 3):

First, writing reinforces the grammatical structures, idioms and vocabulary that we have been teaching our students.

Second, when our students write, they also have a chance to be adventurous with the language, to go beyond what they have just learned to say, to take risk.

Third, when they write, they necessarily become very involved with the new language; the effort to express ideas and the constant use of eye, hand and brain is a unique way to reinforce learning.

4. Three Sub-skills

4.1 Pronunciation

Pronunciation is the way we produce verbal signals of a word or sentence. It is one of the most important sub-skills of a language. It is inextricably connected to speaking which ensures production of speech sounds meant for the expression of meaning. It includes discrete sound segments manifested as vowels and consonants, and suprasegmental features such as stress, intonation, rhythm, voice quality and expressive idiosyncrasy.

Accurate pronunciation is important to be understood by native speakers. But L2 learners often lag behind in attaining accuracy in pronunciation. It is usually the largest obstacle to overcome when trying to achieve fluency. Many non-native speakers may have studied grammar for many years, still they may be unable to speak like native speakers due to their inability to pronounce the sounds of words properly with correct accent and intonation.

Knowing grammar and vocabulary are important but pronunciation is much more so. Achieving good pronunciation should be a learner's main goal, according to some methodologies like Audiolingual Method and Direct Method. A learner of English, for example, can realize the importance of good pronunciation by visiting a predominantly English speaking country and talking to the native speakers. To become a better English speaker, one has to talk to native speakers in native-like pronunciation.

Pronunciation teachers of English usually agree that there are three basic levels of pronunciation.

Level-1: People usually do not understand what one is saying.

Level-2: People usually understand what one is saying but one may have to repeat one's statements for clarification.

Level-3: People understand what one is saying the first time. L2 learners strive to attain this level.

4.2 Vocabulary

The term vocabulary refers to the stock of words a language or an individual has. The words may be oral and written and they must be at the disposal of language users. A good stock of words is necessary for anybody engaged in communication. Vocabulary is an essential component for successful communication. Reading helps a lot to enrich vocabulary. Weak vocabulary means weak communication and its lack may result in complete failure to convey a message. David Wilkins (1972) said, "Without grammar very little can be conveyed, without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed." Thornbury (2006) mentions the following features of words:

- i) Words have different functions, some carrying mainly grammatical meaning, while others bear a greater informational load.
- ii) The same word can have a variety of forms.
- iii) Words can be added to, or combined, to form new words.
- iv) Words can group together to form units that behave as if they were single words.
- v) Many words commonly co-occur with other words.
- vi) Words may look and sound the same but have quite different meanings.
- vii) One word may have a variety of overlapping meanings.
- viii) Different words may share similar meanings, or may have opposite meanings.
- ix) Some words can be defined in terms of their relationship with other words, whether, for example, they belong to the same set or co-occur in similar texts.
- i) Words can have the same or similar meanings but be used in different situations or for different effects.

The vocabulary of a language learner develops over time in a slow incremental process as they learn the meaning of words and their application. Some researches show that an average student learns six to eight words per day, accumulating about 3,000 words a year. Most L2 learners will be happy to have acquired 5000 words after several years of study. Learning goals can differ, yet in English “a large vocabulary is required for language use” for communication (Schmitt, 2010). Nation and Meara (2010) argue that 4,000-5,000 word families are required for intermediate level performance in English, and at least 6,000-9,000 for advanced proficiency. Educated native English speakers, in contrast, have some 16,000-20,000 word families in their English vocabularies (Schmitt, 2010).

For vocabulary development, direct interaction is necessary alongside direct instruction. Though the percentage of words learned through direct instruction may sound small, it is significant. Experts agree that a combination of direct instruction and participation in communicative events is the best way to achieving rich vocabulary. Good readers often acquire much of their vocabulary through a wide range of independent reading.

4.3 Grammar

Grammar is defined in literature in the following terms:

- i) Grammar is the study of how words are put together to make a sentence.
- ii) Grammar is the written official rules, coming out conventions, prescribed for any language user.
- iii) Grammar is the branch of linguistics which deals with syntax, morphology and semantics.
- iv) Grammar is the appropriate use of spoken language, i.e. pragmatics.
- v) Grammar is the common core of all human languages.

The fourth definition points to the fact that grammar is not simply rules of a language but it melts down to social, semantic and discourse factors (Celce-Murcia and Hilles, 1988). The fifth definition claims the existence of universal grammar.

There are various types of grammar: Prescriptive grammar, Formal grammar, Descriptive grammar and Functional grammar. Prescriptive grammar prescribes the rules for everyone to follow without questioning. Formal

grammar focuses exclusively on the forms of language. Descriptive grammar describes the nature of language exercised in a society at a particular time. Functional Grammar exclusively focuses on the language functions, in connection to the its practical use.

Grammar is the most crucial part of language competence and often considered central to any teaching/learning initiative. For some, grammar is difficult to learn as they fail to understand how language works while trying to memorize the rules. Some experts prefer implicit grammar to explicit grammar. Grammar is implicit when a language is acquired communicatively with the least reference to rules. It is explicit when the set of rules are discussed openly with the learners.

5. Interlink of the Skills

All the skills are linked to one another. Of the four skills, listening and speaking are directly linked, and so are reading and writing. Of the sub-skills, pronunciation is integrally connected to listening and speaking, and vocabulary and grammar to reading and writing. From the perspective of communication channel, listening and reading are receptive, and speaking and writing are productive, since the former two involve reception of audiovisual signals by the listener/reader, and the latter two involve transmission or production of audiovisual signals by the speaker/writer. The listener/speaker/reader/writer can be a single individual just playing different roles in different situations.

Though in a segregated skills model, contrary to ours, the skills are treated separately, but practically no skill can be realized without the other, particularly in receptive/productive sense. When listening is practiced, speaking comes automatically, and vice versa. When we talk of reading, there must be a product of writing, and again writing comes after certain amount of reading. We may establish the interlink of the skills with another example, A person has read a book (reading), he has taken note from it (writing), he has talked about it (speaking) and the audience has listened to the talks (listening). Because of interlinking of skills, it is better to treat them together.

The sub-skills are also related to each other and to the four major skills. Though pronunciation is basically a listening/speaking phenomenon, it may also be connected to reading and writing; for example, every written word and sentence can be pronunciation and really done so when read aloud.

Vocabulary and grammar are thought to be closely connected to reading and writing, but there is no denial of their connection to listening and speaking. When somebody is listening to a discourse, he/she must realize it in terms of words and their organization. In one sense, vocabulary may be considered to be the center of gravity in the cluster of skills. Lexical items are the basic building blocks of a language, the fact being emphasized by Lewis (1993), “Lexis is the core or heart of language”. From a central location, vocabulary links up all other skills and sub-skills. The interlink of the skills and sub-skills can shown in the following way:

Figure-2: Interlink of the skills

6. Principles of Integration

Integration is not simply haphazard ordering of skills practice. Rather it is a systematic scheme which allows sequencing of materials and their practice in a coherent way. Nunan (1989) suggest how an effective language lesson can incorporate a range of different factors that ought to maximize language learning potential; he calls it ‘the integrated language lesson’. Developing a unit of material to practice the integration of language skills in the context of a restaurant, he drafts the following seven design principles:

- i) *Authenticity*: A tape containing authentic interaction between a waiter and a restaurant customer for learners to listen to.
- ii) *Task continuity*: One activity builds on what went before; for example, listening leads on to reading and discussion.
- iii) *Real-world focus*: The materials make an explicit link between the classroom and the real world.

- iv) *Language focus*: Learners are systematically exposed to the language system and are encouraged to identify patterns and regularities through discovery learning.
- v) *Learning focus*: The tasks develop the skills of self-monitoring and self-evaluation.
- vi) *Language practice*: The activity gives the opportunity to learners to, for example, have controlled oral work practice.
- vii) *Problem solving*: Learners work in pairs or in small groups to try to facilitate language acquisition.

We may keep all the points in mind when we are involved in teaching/learning activities. We may implement them in our classroom procedure. When we are planning an integration of various skills in a language course, we need to follow some broad guiding principles. We suggest adherence to the following five principles:

1. All the skills and sub-skills are covered in a balanced way and in sufficient amount.
2. The skills are properly sequenced so that one smoothly flows into another, the best sequence being listening-speaking-reading-writing on a broader plain.
3. The lessons are planned in such a way that a single class slot can involve all/maximum skills practices.
4. The activities under a particular lesson (covered in a class) will be interlinked so that subsequent practices will be 'additive' to the previous practices.
5. The integrated lessons ensure maximal learning, providing the learners with all-round language development in all areas of proficiency.

7. Lp-Sp-Rvg-Wvg Model

The Lp-Sp-Rvg-Wvg Model integrates all the four skills and three sub-skills in a particular sequence so that maximum benefits are derived from it when practiced in a language classroom. The uppercase L-S-R-W mean listening, speaking, reading and writing and lowercase p, v and g mean pronunciation, vocabulary and grammar respectively. The model is spelled out in the following flowchart:

Figure-3: Skills flowchart

In our model, listening is the springboard, from which language practices will be initiated, and other skills crop up in a chain. The lesson will start with listening whereby the students will be acquainted with the modes of pronunciation. Next, speaking will provide the students with the scope of practice of what they have listened including pronunciation. Then, they will look at the script of what they have listened and spoken. They read it and learn related vocabulary and grammar. At the final stage, they write a composition or so where they will apply words and structural rules they have learned.

The skills are sequenced based on the hypothesis of natural order. In the first language acquisition, children first listen to whatever sounds appear around their ears; gradually they produce basic sounds and words; as they grow up they learn how to read; and finally they learn how to write. This natural order has been replicated in the present model.

8. Implementing the Model: An Example

We give an example of how the Lp-Sp-Rvg-Wvg Model is implemented in the classroom. We take a lesson from Ann Baker's *Sheep or Ship*.

- i) **Lp (Listening and pronunciation):** If we look at any unit of the book, we will find there are some taped elements. If we take, for example Unit-11 (pages 34-37), the teacher will play Practice-1 and Practice-2 and the students will listen and repeat. The students should be able to distinguish between the short and long vowels exemplified by such pairs as: sheep/ship, pull/pool. The teacher will notice whether the students can

pronounce the words properly (it necessarily involves a bit of speaking). He will help those who have problems in pronunciation, making them aware of the length of vowels and the use of vocal organs. They will also be made aware of how pronouncing words in varying vowel length makes a difference in meaning. The teacher, if he/she wishes, may test their improvement in listening and pronunciation, with the given "Test" item. For further listening practice, the teacher will play "Stress" section, making them aware of the importance of stress. The students will practice until they attain a desired level of perfection.

- ii) Sp (Speaking and pronunciation):** Listening will lead to speaking practice. The students will listen to the dialogue "In a good school" in the same Unit and practice it in group. They may dramatize it, taking different roles like Prue, Sue and June. The teacher himself/herself can act in the role of Miss Luke. They may practice it several times. This dialogue practice may be followed by conversation practice. The teacher may pick up the following piece of conversation from Stress practice:

A: Excuse me.

B: Yes?

A: Could you tell me where I can get some good shoelaces?

B: Yes. There's a shop next to the supermarket that sells very good shoelaces. I'm going there too.

The teacher may create a gap in the conversation as follows:

A: Could you tell me where I can get some good -----?

B: Yes. There's a shop next to the ----- that sells very good ----- . I'm going there too.

The teacher may provide a list of relevant words/phrases (for example: toothpaste, fruit juice, cookery, books, grocery store, fruit shop, book shop) which the students will use to fill up the gaps in the conversation.

- iii) Rvg (Reading, vocabulary and grammar):** The teacher will now ask the students to read the dialogue and conversation. The students will be asked to pick up particular words which they do not understand or which need explanation. They may pick up such words as 'rude' or 'nuisance'.

The teacher will make their meaning clear. He/she may pick words himself/herself and show how they change their forms and how they are used in sentences. For example, he/she may choose the word 'threw'. The teacher may explain that it is the past form of the verb 'throw' and its past participle form is 'thrown'. He/she may make three sentences like these to show how the three forms are used in different sentences: 1. She throws the paper in the basket; 2. She threw the paper in the basket; 3. She has thrown the paper in the basket. For a little more grammar practice, the teacher may also show them how the sentences are converted into negative and interrogative sentences, like: 1. She does not throw the paper in the basket; 2. She did not throw the paper in the basket, 3. She has not thrown the paper in the basket; 4. Does she throw the paper in the basket; 5. Did she throw the paper in the basket; 6. Has she thrown the paper in the basket. The teacher may use the dialogue as a piece for reading comprehension. He/she may ask some questions to measure the level of comprehension of the students.

- iv) **Wvg (Writing, vocabulary and grammar):** At this stage, the teacher will engage students in writing activities. The teacher may ask the students to make sentences of their own based on given vocabulary, e.g. afternoon, soup, look, foot, boot, etc. The teacher may ask them to write similar dialogues as they have practiced. It may be "In the playground", "In the supermarket" or "In the library". Or the students will write a paragraph on the playground, supermarket or library. Or they may narrate their one day's experience in a specified location. The teacher will help the students in writing tasks, giving them directions and clues for elaboration. He/she check the written scripts, with particular attention to organization of content, choice of vocabulary and structure of sentences. He/she will provide feedback, where necessary, to improve their writing skills. At an advanced level, the teacher asks them to write short story or essay on specific topics that came in discussion.

The lesson at issue will be schematized in the following flowchart:

Figure-4: A lesson with integrated skills

If we put the flowchart in a timeframe of a class, it will be realized as a lesson plan. In a class of two hours, the lesson will be divided as follows:

Skill	Time	Activity
Listening	30 minutes	Listening of word pairs and dialogue/Pronunciation practice of vowel length and stress
Speaking	30 minutes	Speaking practice with dialogue and conversation/ Word and sentence pronunciation in focus
Reading	30 minutes	Reading the dialogue/ Clarifying word forms and meaning/Sentence formation and transformation/Reading comprehension
Writing	30 minutes	Making sentences with selected words/Writing dialogue, paragraph or essay

9. Conclusion

In this way, as stated above, all the skills and sub-skills will be integrated in lesson unit whereby the students are expected to be highly benefited. The classes will be interactive, on a par with the principles of Communicative Language Teaching. The knowledge of the language will be synthesized in a harmonious manner through concerted practice. It should be kept in mind that language skills are often naturally overlapped and combined. For example, speaking and listening can hardly be separated. Similarly, writing is often preceded by reading. The teacher's responsibility is to systematize the combinations and ensure maximum learning of language. The model presented here is not however impervious to permutation. The teacher is allowed to utilize his/her own sense to permute skills as per the necessity of the students. The teacher must choose materials according to the level of the students and engage them in practices appropriate for them.

References

- Baker, Ann. (1981). *Ship or Sheep? An Intermediate Pronunciation Course*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Barman, B. and Basu, B. L. (2015). *Approaches and Methods of Language Teaching*. Dhaka: Friends Book Corner.
- Bygate, Martin. (2008). *Speaking*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Celce-Murcia, M. and Hilles, S. (1988). *Techniques and Resources in Teaching Grammar*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

- Gebhard, Jerry, J. (2009). *Teaching English as a Foreign or Second Language*. Michigan: The University of Michigan Press.
- Grabe, W. and Stoller, F. L. (2011). *Teaching and Researching Reading*. New Delhi: Pearson Education.
- Hedge, Tricia. (2005). *Writing*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Hughes, Rebecca. (2011). *Teaching and Researching Speaking*. New Delhi: Pearson Education.
- Hyland, Ken. (2011). *Teaching and Researching Writing*. New Delhi: Pearson Education.
- Lewis, M. (1993). *The lexical approach: The state of ELT and a way forward*. Hove, UK: Language Teaching Publications.
- Lubelska, D. and Matthews, M. (1997). *Looking at Language Classrooms*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Lynch, Tony. (2007). *Study Listening*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- McDonough, J. and Shaw, C. (2004). *Materials and Methods in ELT*. Malden, MA: Blackwell Publishing.
- Nation, P. and Meara, P. (2010). Vocabulary. In N. Schmitt (Ed.), *An introduction to applied linguistics* (2nd ed.) (pp. 252-267). London: Hodder Education.
- Nunan, David. (1989). *Designing Tasks for the Communicative Classroom*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Oxford, Rebecca. (2001). Integrated Skills in the ESL/EFL Classroom. *ESL Magazine*, 4 (1), 18-20.
- Raimes, Ann. (1983). *Techniques in Teaching Writing*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Richards, J. C. Platt, J. and Weber, H. (1985). *Longman Dictionary of Applied Linguistics*. London: Longman.
- Rivers, Wilga. (1968). *Teaching Foreign Language Skills*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.
- Rost, Michael. (1990). *Listening in Language Learning*. London: Longman.
- Rost, Michael. (2011). *Teaching and Researching Listening*. New Delhi: Pearson Education.
- Schmitt, N. (2010). *Researching vocabulary: A vocabulary research manual*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Silberstein, Sandra. (1994). *Techniques and Resources in Teaching Reading*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Thornbury, Scott. (2006). *How to teach vocabulary*. New Delhi: Longman.
- Turk, Christopher. (2003). *Effective Speaking*. London: Spon Press.
- Wallace, Catherine. (2010). *Reading*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Welty, Eudora. (2002). *On Writing*. New York: Modern Library.
- White, Goodith. (2008). *Listening*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Wilkins, D. (1972). *Linguistics in language teaching*. London: Arnold.
- Williams, E. (1984). *Reading in the Language Classroom*. London: Macmillan.